

INFLUENCE OF PLY ORIENTATION ON THE MEASUREMENT OF MODE II DELAMINATION

T. Vu Khanh, R. Langlois

(National research council of Canada, Industrial Materials Research Institute, Boucherville, Québec, Canada, J4B 6Y4)

R. Gauvin

(Ecole Polytechnique de Montréal, C.P. 6079, Succ. A., Montréal, Québec, Canada)

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the effect of ply orientation on the measurements of mode II static and fatigue delamination energies, using the common flexural sample. It is shown that the crack always deviates from its mid-thickness location, due to the fracture of θ° ply. Crack deviation results in significant error in the determination of mode II delamination energy, due to the presence of mode I and additional friction. Conditions for pure mode II measurements are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The methodologies for experimental measurements of mode II delamination energy have been well established. The most widely used method is that based on flexural specimens (1-8) in which the data reduction schemes are based on beam theory. Although it has been shown that global analysis using beam theory underestimates G_{IIc} by 20-40% (8), global analysis is still widely used because of its simplicity and the conservative measured value of delamination energy.

Basically, delamination is an interlaminar fracture problem. Because of high anisotropies of laminae, interlaminar stresses develop between layers of different fiber orientation (9-12). In the presence of these stresses and under some circumstances, delamination occurs. Even though mismatch in elastic properties of individual plies have been well related to interlaminar stresses, surprisingly, the effect of ply orientation on delamination resistance of laminated composites is not known.

The purpose of this work is to analyze the validity of flexural samples for the analysis of the effect of ply orientation on mode II delamination energy. The inconsistency of the results in the presence of different ply orientations in the sample will be demonstrated. The influence of incoherent factors such as friction force and the existence of mode I on both static and fatigue delamination measurements will be discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental measurements were carried out on glass/epoxy laminates (Ferro CE-9000-9/S-2 Prepreg). Two types of stacking sequences were used: a quasi-homogeneous cross-ply laminate and a 28-ply $[+\theta_n, -\theta_n, 0_{14-4n}, -\theta_n, +\theta_n]$ laminate where θ° take the value 0, 15, 30, 45, 60 and 90°, $n = 1$ or 2. The plates were laid up by hand and fabricated in an autoclave according to the supplier's

recommended cure procedures. Beams of 10 mm width containing different crack lengths were subsequently cut out from these plates, parallel to the 0 degree direction. The initial crack was either clamped or let free as discussed previously (13).

The static tests were performed on an Instron machine, Model 1125, at a cross-head speed of 10 mm/min. The fatigue tests were carried out under force control, on a MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine, Model 810, equipped with a 1 kN load cell. The tests were conducted at a frequency of 7 Hz, a ratio of maximum to minimum loads of 0.1, ambient temperature and 50% relative humidity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The first observation that could be made on the effect of ply orientation is that except for $\theta = 0$ and 15° , the crack always deviates from its original plane to reach the 0° layer, in both static and fatigue loadings. This effect has been observed when the mid-plane layer is at 90° with respect to the crack growth direction (13). Moreover the direction of crack deviation depends on the type of specimen used, i.e. the crack deviates toward the upper half of the sample in the case of clamped edge crack and toward the lower half in the case of free edge crack specimens. From this observation, a qualitative explanation of the crack deviation is possible: due to the presence of longitudinal stress, induced by bending moment and enhanced by stress concentration effect at the crack tip, fracture of θ° ply occurs on the tensile stress side of the crack face. As a consequence, in free-edge-crack samples, the crack deviates toward the lower half of the sample which undergoes a tensile stress. In clamped edge crack specimens, it has been previously shown (13) that, at the crack tip, the condition of continuity of the cross section of the beam leads to a negative moment, resulting in a positive normal stress at the upper face of the crack. Crack growth therefore occurs toward the upper part of the sample.

In fact crack deviation in Mode II fracture has been explained in a more fundamental way. The strain energy density criterion (14,15) suggests that fracture occurs when the local minimum component $(dW/dV)_m$ of the strain energy density reaches a critical value. $(dW/dV)_m$ has been calculated for the shear Mode II in isotropic materials (15). The calculation results show that the crack should propagate at an angle of about -82.3° for a Poisson's ratio of 0.3 with respect to its initial plane.

The investigation of the effect of ply orientation on mode II delamination consists therefore mainly in measuring the separation energy between θ° and 0° layers. It is also obvious that in such flexural tests, delamination is no longer in a pure mode II because of the difference between the rigidities and consequently between the curvatures of the sub beams above and below the crack surface. The experimental results show that in such conditions, the static toughness in mode II delamination, G_{II} continuously decreases with increasing θ° , from about 2kJ/m^2 for $\theta = 0$ to 0.5kJ/m^2 for $\theta = 90^\circ$. On the other hand, under fatigue loading at a given ΔG_{II} value, the crack propagation rate decreases with θ° , attains a lowest rate at $\theta = 45^\circ$ and increases with increasing θ° . It is worth noting that these results are only of limited value since the effect of crack location on the G_{II} value, as measured by flexural samples, is not known.

In order to verify the validity of the pure mode II when the crack is not located at the mid-plane, static and fatigue tests were carried out on a quasi-homogeneous cross-ply laminate in which the plane of the crack was varied through the thickness. The strain energy release rate in the sample was determined from the global analysis of the potential energy. The potential energy was calculated by dividing the specimen into three parts as discussed previously (13). The calculation of the strain energy release rate as a function of crack length and crack-plane location for the free-edge-crack unbalanced specimen gives:

$$G_{II} = \frac{6P^2a^2}{E_x^f b^3 h^3} \left[\frac{\varphi^2}{y^3} + \frac{(1-\varphi)^2}{(1-y)^3} - 1 \right]$$

$$\varphi \equiv \frac{y^3}{y^3 + (1-y)^3} ; y = \frac{h_1}{h}$$

- a = Crack length
- b = Specimen width
- E_x^f = Effective flexural modulus
- h_1 = Upper beam thickness
- h = Specimen thickness
- P = External load

The verification of the specimen compliance, derived from the potential energy, revealed that the calculation is in very good agreement with experimental measurements. Figures 1 and 2 show the effect of crack-plane location on G_{IIc} . In figure 1, good linear relationships are observed, suggesting that the above equation for the global strain energy release rate as a function of crack length and crack location is valid. Figure 2 shows that as the crack plane is moved from the upper face ($h_1/h = 0$, where h_1 is the thickness of the upper sub-beam and h is the total thickness of the sample) to the lower face of the sample ($h_1/h = 1$), G_{IIc} strongly increases.

Figure 1: Determination of the critical strain energy release rate (G_{IIc}) for 3 crack different crack plane locations.

Figure 2: Variation of the delamination energy (G_{IIc}) as a function of the plane location.

The measurement of fatigue crack propagation also revealed the same effect of crack location on crack growth resistance. Figure 3 presents the plots of crack propagation rate, da/dN , as a function of G_{IIc} for different crack plane locations, h_1/h . At a given crack propagation rate below 0.002, the crack growth resistance, as determined by the flexural specimen, increases with increasing h_1/h .

To determine the possible factors which could cause the above increase in G_{IIc} three parameters have been analyzed; the longitudinal normal stress induced by bending moment, the friction force at the loading point and the presence of mode I of fracture. The maximum longitudinal normal stress at the crack tip has been calculated by neglecting the stress concentration effect and is shown in Figure 4. The result shows that the maximum value of the longitudinal normal stresses increase with h_1/h , attain a maximum value and then, decrease with increasing h_1/h . This variation is not consistent with the continuous variation of G_{IIc} with h_1/h . The longitudinal normal stresses are therefore most probably not responsible for the variation of G_{IIc} .

Figure 3: Fatigue crack growth data for 3 different crack plane locations.

Figure 4: Variation of the longitudinal normal stress at the crack tip for the upper and lower faces as a function of crack plane location.

The analysis of the contact force at the loading point between the two sub-beams of the sample revealed that the contact force continuously decreases with increasing h_1/h . Consequently friction at the loading point should diminish with increasing h_1/h and not cause the increase in G_{IIc} .

To determine the presence of the mode I in the sample, the curvatures of the upper and lower faces of the crack, at the crack tip region, have been calculated. The calculation was made by considering each sub-beam of the sample as a cantilever beam and that it can deform freely under load. It is worth noting that the latter assumption does not represent the real condition in the sample. In fact, due to the contact force, distributed over a certain length at the loading point, the cross sections of the two sub-beams at the loading point cannot freely rotate. This constraint affects the curvatures of the sub-beams, as calculated from the above assumptions. However this consideration has been made in order to verify the existence of normal stress through the specimen thickness, at the crack tip. Figure 5 shows the variation of these curvatures as a function of h_1/h . The result clearly demonstrates that, due to the difference in these curvatures, the mode I should exist in the sample.

Figure 5: Variation of the curvatures of the two sub-beams as a function of the crack plane location.

The measured fracture energies are that of a mixed mode and depend on the values of G_I and G_{II} . Furthermore the mismatch in curvatures could create additional friction outside the loading point region which increases the inaccuracy of the measurement. Further evidence of the presence of G_I is given in figure 6a, which shows that the two faces of the crack separated when the specimen is loaded and $h_1/h \neq 1/2$. It is also worth noting that at $h_1/h = 1/2$, the two curvatures are equal (Figure 6b) and the pure mode II can be obtained. In order to properly measure the pure mode II delamination energy, samples of identical flexural rigidities above and below the crack surface must be used.

Figure 6: Edge of the cantilever beam under load.
a) $h_1/h = 6/28$; b) $h_1/h = 1/2$

CONCLUSION

It has been shown that to measure the mode II delamination energy between plies other than two 0° plies, care must be taken in using the common flexural specimen. The crack always deviates from its initial plane to reach a 0° ply before delamination occurs. The measurement of mode II delamination between θ° and 0° plies requires the use of an unbalanced sample. In such conditions, due to the difference between the curvatures of the two crack surfaces, the contribution of mode I exists and strongly affects the measured value of delamination energy. Other frictions than that at the loading point region also become significant. Pure mode II delamination must be carried out on samples of equal flexural rigidities above and below the crack plane.

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